

Infrastructural Development and Maintenance in Nigeria

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Abstract

The development of infrastructure and its maintenance is an important aspect of the growth of society and economy. The functionality and sustainability of their infrastructure facilities result in the progression of the people, which ultimately leads to the improvement in the society and economy of the country. Nigeria possesses a population of 195 million and faces serious issues regarding the infrastructure development and its maintenance. The paper discusses the progress which is made by the government for improving the subparts of infrastructure including, health, education, agriculture, transport, energy and water supply, information technology and communication. For the maintenance of this development, corrective, preventive and improvement in the maintenance are considered. The paper highlighted that government of Nigeria is spending almost \$25 billion towards the infrastructure development annually. However, the country requires an amount of almost \$2900 billion to fulfil its integrated Development Plan until 2044. For identifying average investment and issues related to them, previous studies and research papers are evaluated to conclude the difficulties faced by the Government of Nigeria regarding the development of infrastructure. It is also concluded in the paper that government is now considering the idea of Public-Private-Partnership (PPP), to improve the framework of the country. The recommendations for incorporating well-developed strategies is also provided which includes the policies regarding the prioritised units for investment, which covers the basic needs of people. Furthermore, policies regarding other sub-areas, such as availability of information technology and ease of communication are also provided.

Keywords: Infrastructure Development, Maintenance, Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) Sustainability.

Introduction

The developed infrastructure is significant for countries to undergo social and economic growth as highlighted by (African Development Bank, 2018), the significant discrepancy in the infrastructure of Africa has eventually augmented the cost of production and transaction and accompanied with an adverse effect on the foreign investment flow. The national development would be a dream without investing in country's infrastructure, therefore the countries like Japan, South Korea then followed by China commenced a drastic enhancement in the country's infrastructure in order to attain sustainable economic growth (Ackah, 2018). The extent of development in basic infrastructure of Nigeria can be easily identified by its physical and organisational structures such as industries, health, transportation, communication, and the quality of governance as the infrastructure serves as an interconnected structural elements that provides the supporting framework of entire development structure (Sullivan & Sheffrin, 2003; Oyedele, 2016).

Background

The deficit in the infrastructure of Africa shall be analysed in the context of capital scarcity, there is a persistent shortage of all sort of built capital related to stock of housing, commercial and industrial structures, in addition around 80% population in most of the African cities are living in informal housing (Collier & Venables, 2016). It is estimated that almost 62 percent of the urban population of Africa have limited access to water and they are spending their lives in slums, while the provision of public services such as water supply, sanitation, health, and education are generally weak (Habitat, 2015; Foster & Briceño-Garmendia, 2010). According to Nigeria, N. (2018), In the mid of 2017, it was reported that around 1.25 billion people lived in Africa while Nigeria was declared to be the most populous nation among all the countries of Africa, the projected population of Nigeria by 2050 will let the nation to attain third highest rank in the world.

The productivity is considered as the essence for national development, whereas the radical improvements are indeed and critical for attaining higher productivity marks. Kathmandu Final Workshop Report (2009) elaborates the effectiveness of infrastructure; it is helpful in the execution of problems related to national health, development, economics and social. The reason that western countries are more advanced than African countries is that they possess standardised and better physical infrastructure with the quality of transportation and other elements of infrastructure they have clocked prompt economic growth (Collier & Venables, 2016; Ackah, 2018). In order to overcome the infrastructure development and maintenance challenges, the government of Nigeria is spending \$25 billion while the estimated amount required in the accomplishment of an integrated development plan by 2044 is around \$2900 billion. Now, the government is focused to practice Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) in order to mitigate the flaws in the framework of the country Nigeria's infrastructure development and maintenance (2018).

The purpose of the Study

Despite the fact that government of Nigeria seems to take an active part in economic development by spending a decent amount of resources, the unequal distribution of income, political instability, and low standard of transportation is route cause of its underdeveloped infrastructure. The study evaluates the methods used by the Government of Nigeria to mitigate the barriers in its infrastructural development with an approach to experience faster economic growth.

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Literature Review

The definition of infrastructure is not standardised due to three analytical objectives: The formation of concept, the integration of theoretical approaches and the explanation on the grounds of the reality of infrastructure establishment, the term incorporates roads, education, manufacturing, agricultural and activities related to mining (Torrise, 2009). An increase in the investment on development of country's infrastructure eventually increases the output even if the productivity is not improved hence it is referred as the function of output and infrastructure is formed according to experience the welfare improvements in the nation (Infrastructure and development, 2018). Sustainable infrastructures are sole important to improve the quality of life within a country, the development is focused to the betterment of designing, building and operating while considering the economic, financial, environmental and social values. The integrated development of infrastructure and finance are crucial elements in the economic sustainable economic growth (Saghir, 2017).

As identified by Festus & Amos (2015) housing is the referred to the necessity of living and contributes in the development of infrastructure, most of the people in Nigeria are spending their lives in informal houses while homelessness and deficient environmental condition are commonly observed inside the nation. The ways to overcome the issues of the housing defining the policy instrument can be the key; the plan of action may include proper labour management, utilization of technology, providing housing finance and allocating the houses with regular monitoring. While conceiving the Nigerian policy along with the fundamental elements of feasibility and affordability in order to make appropriate enhancements in the production and delivery of better housing facility throughout the country (Festus & Amos, 2015).

As the better housing policy provides the people better standard of living, on the other hand, it is health, food and clothing are fundamental to welfare and survival, as particularized by Dabara et al (2016) the physical framework of providing goods and services facilities to the public is also referred as infrastructure. Furthermore, it also covers the wide range of services related to education, medical, agriculture, water supply, savage, road, energy and other facilities accompanied by its contribution in the national economic development through increasing the productivity and enhances the standard of living with the amenities. The evaluation of financing, infrastructure and urban development, the Nigerian infrastructure highlights the wide spectrum of services and ultimately influences economic development with enhancement in productivity; as a result, there exist immense needs of development in infrastructural amenities (Dabara et al, 2016).

Based on assessing the needs of infrastructure development, it is identified that facilities of transportation, waste management, and electricity water supply are not very commendable in Nigeria. It is clear that government alone is not sufficient to shoulder the concerns hence the involvement of private sector is imperative (Dabara et al, 2016; Idris & Salisu, 2016). According to Idris & Salisu (2016), the rate of corruption in Nigeria is very high and is responsible for the poor condition of infrastructural development and maintenance in the county. The implication of policy is indeed for enabling the government of Nigeria to effectively utilise the integrated strategies that shall be aimed at blocking the leakages in the system of anti-corruption, strengthening the laws of anti-corruption and attain the judicial reforms. In order to provide the sustenance of infrastructure within Nigeria, it is significant to embark on structural reforms in order to strengthen the regulatory standards whereas the participation of citizen would be the key in these transformations (Idris & Salisu, 2016).

Lawal (2014) refers the infrastructural development as the most critical stage, the empowered countries in the world to guarantee the quality of livelihoods of the citizens and enhance their quality of living, furthermore he highlights the point that infrastructure plays significant role in political development, living standard's enrichment and developing the socio-economic framework of the country. According to Lawal (2014), Nigeria is highly focused to infrastructure delivery at the local level as most of the population resides in local areas, he further specifies that less than 40 percent of Nigerian population have access to safe and healthy water resources, electricity supply and developed framework of roads. Despite all the challenges faced by Nigeria, the application of PPPs in the recent era have become very popular and is considered a crucial element in the overall development and management of required amenities (Mudi, Lowe & Manase, 2015).

Some of the facilities have developed with the implementation of PPPs such as roads infrastructure; however, the overall operation is failed in terms of effectiveness and functionality. No doubt, the government of Nigeria with this approach made the great effort to the implementation of PPPs with the integration of appropriate mechanisms and defined framework but unfortunately, the strategy failed and needs to be transformed in order to enhance its infrastructure project development (Mudi, Lowe & Manase, 2015). Festus & Amos (2015) have highlighted the point that what can Africa learn from China in terms of infrastructural development, it is understood that China has undergone rapid development of its infrastructure and revolutionized to offer cost-effective industrial solutions. The strategy can be drawn based on the useful lessons learned from the development of China that would be effective in the identification and elimination of market failures and binding constraints. Today many countries are facing different microenvironment and many African countries are the destination of transfer of industries from the region of East Asia, to improve the business environment Africa shall focus on their tax niceties.

According to Festus & Amos (2015), Nigeria shall focus on the provision of better business environment incorporated with effective services such as good infrastructure in order to meet the constraints of doing business. The nation shall overcome the power shortage issues and other problems related to slow customs, inadequate roads, and supply of clean water as China is capable of providing better infrastructures and high-quality services in most of its zones. All those zones are very attractive to the investors and furthermore, one thing Africans can do differently from China is attracting massive private investments with the developed framework of PPP, whereas the traditional framework engages the utilization of limited resources from the government of Nigeria as China is also moving towards this direction (Festus & Amos, 2015).

Conclusion

Main Findings

The purpose of research is directed to evaluate the methods, which are utilised in Nigeria for mitigating the barriers to the development of its infrastructure. The activities used by Nigerian Government have been analysed in the research. The findings of the research are analysed on the premise of different infrastructural projects including Water, Health, Education, Agriculture, Transport, Communication, Electricity, energy and information.

Figure 1: Infrastructure. (Source; Ibikunle, 2014)

The research findings can be interpreted based on statistical findings generated by Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku (2012). The paper shows that Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) is an important method, which was utilised by the Nigerian government in its infrastructural development. Nevertheless, the suitability of PPP is different infrastructure projects can be different. The statistical analysis of the research supports the fact that transportation system including railways, airports and roads are ranked highest. These are mainly executed based on PPPs. However, provision of electricity and water is ranked as 2nd for the suitability of PPPs. Environmental, natural resources are ranked on 3rd as well as health, and social services are at 4th. Leisure, tourism and cultural, real estate as well as educational projects are mainly not suitable based on PPP method. Real estate and educational construction projects ranked lowest in terms of suitability of execution using PPPs.

Findings produced by Foster & Briceño-Garmendia (2010) can be used to support the above results. It has been assessed that water supply, sanitation, health and education provision is improper in Africa. The reason is that PPP is not suitable for this infrastructural project but the government has utilised them. Moreover, it has been assessed that 62 % of African population who resides in Urban areas have limited or no access to water and other basic facilities. However, the study of Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku (2012) has provided ANOVA results, which shows the fact that PPP projects are not significant in every type of infrastructural project as it is not suitable for each type.

The statistical results can be interpreted based on results produced by Nigeria (2018). It has been assessed that almost 1.25 billion population resides in Africa but Nigeria is considered as a most popular region of it. Due to this fact, the government has spent almost \$25 billion for the development of Nigerian infrastructure. The Development Plan of the country creates a requirement of almost \$2900 billion investments until the year of 2044. According to Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku (2012), one of the methods of evaluating the impact of projects on the infrastructural development is the utilisation of different critical success factors. These factors can include competitive procurement process, assessment of cost and benefits in a realistic, favourable framework, risk sharing, stable macroeconomic conditions as well as other factors. Moreover, the proper distribution of authority among the public and private sector can also exert a strong impact on the infrastructural development.

Ibikunle (2014) generated the findings based on secondary data collection method. The research shows that different phases of infrastructural development are vital to seek

sustainability in the projects. The first phase is about designing the infrastructure, which is considered as a least expensive phase in the project. In Africa, infrastructure projects mainly face issues due to the less qualified experts in project design. Poor handling in the design stage and improper management practices can create a shortfall in the project. Construction stage is the second stage of the project and materials are procured, equipment is acquired as well as necessary labour are employed in the project. The good designing stage can be adversely affected due to the improper construction practices of the project. The findings generated in the research demonstrates the fact that inexperienced contractors can face issues to meet the needs of the infrastructural design. In addition, African project largely depends upon the quality of materials and use of poor quality materials can adjourn a negative impact on the outcomes. The last stage is about the usage of the project in operations and for the public use. However, misuse can create damages in it.

On the other hand, the findings generated by Kathmandu Final Workshop Report (2009) provides a clarification that infrastructure projects should be effective enough so that they can play a supporting role in improving the execution of health and other social needs of people. Improvements in transportation can play an important role in economic growth of the country.

Implications

From the above-mentioned findings, following implications have been drawn which can be used for the government of Nigeria in developing effective strategies for infrastructural development.

- It is necessary that the natural endowments, which are present in the rural areas of Nigeria, should be utilised in an effective way so that they can contribute effectively to the productivity of the country. It is because these resources are necessary for the implementation of the economic base in w each of the rural setup (Adenipekun, 2013).
- To estimate the basic relationship between state and municipal economies, especially in the urban areas fabricating the sector and improving the building, which integrates the model of coordinated development to promote the typical city and promote the self-being of this area. The long-term implications of modern urbanisation will fit an existing rural economy to meet urban needs (Oyedele, 2012).
- As the financial base of the country's economy improves, small and medium enterprises will need to be strengthened to local business needs in the region. Institutional frameworks will require a development pattern. The central government must provide the continuous conditions for managing markets in the world for the launch of rural and mineral products as well as tourism (Adenipekun, 2013). A country in African culture is synonymous with life and the assumption of all financial benefits. The government must examine the institutional system and access to assets that allow private landowners to determine the full financial profit of the land. To do so, the ability of real estate surveyors and residents is most important in all local government authorities in Nigeria for successful and effective management and valuation of real estate assets (Babatunde & Perera, 2017).
- In any case, as part of Nigeria, despite its vision to become a major economy in 2020, the country's infrastructure is in a state of decay. It should be manufactured with the ultimate goal specifically to achieve its vision and meet some of the goals to promote poverty reduction goals 2015. Although some scholars may argue that despite the interest in the order of infrastructure,

the country has recorded the achievements of monetary development over the years, it does not contribute to the economic improvement. Since the agricultural land represents an extension of the financial government, as agriculture is still affected by the level of existence, it does not create enough revenue that can have a significant impact on the lack of unemployment (Adenipekun, 2013).

- Policymakers should also promote economic progress by ensuring property rights and political credibility. The right to property is the ability of individuals to practice as an owner on their assets. Property rights are guaranteed when there is a politician, but when there are failures and volatility, there is a question about property rights and insurance, which will lead to the collapse of the morale of venture capital funds and local cash, which will prevent the way of life of the country (Oyedele, 2012).

- Nigeria needs to improve its status on the list of simple universal states turns by moving from the current three digits to the observer states turn top in the top 50 countries with less volatility. Prosperity and the impact of today's high expectations for life were the results of mechanical improvement and interests in innovative work. Although most mechanical progress stems from private research by individual companies and artists, the government must promote the improvement of new developments with creative work by giving companies the opportunity to compute to participate in the creative work and the security framework for obtaining the patent (Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku, 2012).

Limitations

Following are some of the limitations, which can be faced by the government of Nigeria during the implementation of the strategies for the infrastructural development and maintenance.

- **Lack of Visionary Leaders:** Presidents are producers of development, working with creative ability, knowledge and power. They provide the test that reads the best in individuals and unites them around the general sense of mind. It has been observed that the Nigerian economy is suffering in this regard due to which, there is no considerable development observed in the infrastructure of the country (Kumari & Sharma, 2017).

- **Demand and supply:** Due to the weak exhibitions of most of the pioneers in the past, the instability in the context of upgrading the framework overrides the order. Its total land area is 193 million square kilometres, with an area of 9.110 million square kilometres of land over 150 million people. This includes 34,123 km of streets, 30,500 km of state streets and 129,577 km of nearby government streets. Unfortunately, more than 70% of the government's streets are in a terrible state of repair. In the housing sector, Nigeria seeks about 17 million Housing units and 60 trillion nairas, taking into account the ultimate goal of housing needs (Babatunde & Perera, 2017).

- **PESTLE Analysis:** The difficulties of improving infrastructure in Nigeria can be discussed by conducting PESTLE analysis. Difficulties can be infrastructure, political, monetary, social, creative, legal, natural, and welfare. The political situation must be related to the political force, the strategic plan and the legislative issues of the situation at home and abroad. The financial situation manages issues such as loan cost, cash transfer, value fluctuations, etc. (Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku, 2012). The social situation needs the appropriate variety of labour force in which social discrimination, age discrimination, etc. are avoided. Physical environmental issues such as geography, topography, and climatology are also

essential, and the welfare and security of the assets on the site, that is, human, material and financial are necessary. In order to alleviate these problems, Nigeria has no systematic focus on the development of any responsible institution.

There is a need for large management to ensure the successful and effective arrangement of the framework (Babatunde & Perera, 2017).

- **Matrix Development:** The four basic conditions for each physical infrastructure project are: contours, funds, innovation and management. The appropriate programs have not been adopted to ensure cash incentive. The fund is unsatisfactory and secured by high loan fees, and most Nigerian foreign workers require budget management. Innovation in development is rare, and the framework is not enough. Nigeria's improved culture is weak in this way, allowing most of the projects to decay (Olusola Babatunde, Opawole & Emmanuel Akinsiku, 2012).

- **Purchasing method:** Strategies adopted required the interaction. Public funding initiatives, particularly the concession and partnership between the public sector and private sector (PPP) method seems to be impaired and contracts with other people, who are not part of the future action of the program, are voided. Through the development of the Lagos-Abidane road with a length of 105 km, under the partnership agreement between the public sector and the private sector (PPP), the government received the B-Courtney consortium in 2009 compared to N89.53 billion. However, the project did not change the street conditions and goes in vain (Opawole & Jagboro, 2016).

Kumari & Sharma (2017) stated that the political conditions do not push financial experts beyond reach. Governments do not specify the need to promote them. Commitments must meet targets, but for the most part, projects that are designated are not generating enough benefits. It should be noted that the efficient management would be the main antidote that can connect the big hole, which exists between the government and the funding bodies. According to the findings of Adenipekun (2013), Nigeria's general population associated with the streets, the national water supply network will be the task. The exceptional situation of the lack of unemployment is a catalyst for demonstrations and increased capital (Opawole & Jagboro, 2016). It is therefore recommended to design efficient strategies for overcoming all these potential problems so that the implementation of the policies can be ensured.

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